

Assessment of Clothing Care Label Instruction Adherence in Clothing Care by Female Civil Servants in Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State

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Abstract

Adherence to clothing care label instruction in clothing care by Female Civil Servants (FCS) in Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State was studied. The study population comprised Female Civil Servants categorized as women in academics (WA) and those in administrative positions (WAP) in Nsukka LGA. Stratified random sampling technique was adopted to select 160 subjects. Data were collected using questionnaire and analyzed with descriptive statistics. Chi Square (X^2) and t-test statistics tested two hypotheses of the study at 0.05 probability level. Findings reveal that majority of that (93.8%) buy ready to wear garments with care label, 45.2% read care label instructions. None of the FCS (0%) was given or shown care information or instruction when buying fabrics by the yard; none of the 34 identified clothing care label instructions was strictly adhered to by the respondents. There were no significant differences ($P>.05$) in percentage responses of women in academics (WA) and those in administrative positions (WAP) on adherence to washing ($p=0.47$), bleaching ($p=0.80$), dry cleaning ($p=0.42$), drying ($p=0.52$) and ironing ($p=0.56$) at 0.05 level of significance. About 30 problems militating against effective adherence to clothing care label instructions in clothing care by the respondents were identified. There were no significant differences ($P>.05$) in the mean responses of working class women in academics and those in administrative positions on problems relating to washing ($p=0.49$), bleaching ($p=0.57$), dry cleaning ($p=0.49$), drying ($p=0.41$), ironing ($p=0.43$) and manufacturer/fabric sellers' ($p=0.25$) care label instruction adherence in clothing care. Based on the result, it was concluded that Clothing care adherence saves a lot of damage on clothing. Care label instructions were not adhered to by FCS precipitating to 43 identified clothing care instruction adherence related problems encountered in clothing care. Based on the above findings, recommendations were made for clothing and textile manufacturers, retailers and clothing consumers.

Key Words: Clothing Care Label, consumer instruction, clothing condition, mandatory information, fibre content

Introduction

Clothing care refers to various ways of cleaning textile articles to restore to the purchased condition and to make clothing serviceable over a long period of time. Textile articles are yarns, piece goods and made-up articles such as apparel, household textiles, furnishings, upholstery, upholstered furniture or bedding containing at least 80% by mass textile material (British Standards Institution in Reham & Kang, 2018). By law, according to US Federal Trade

Commission and International Standard Organization (ISO), all manufacturers producing ready-to-wear garments and fabrics sold by the yard (piece goods) are required to attach care label to those products.

Care label is a permanent label or tag containing regular care information or instruction that is attached in such a manner that it will not become separated from the clothes but will remain legible during the useful life of the product

(Johnson and Foster, 1990). It is a labeling system instructing consumers to the ideal conditions of caring for the purchased item, mainly laundry process (Shin, 2000). Care label information may be mandatory or voluntary. Mandatory information are those information the manufacturer must make available for consumers such as fibre content, percentage of fibre by weight, identification of the manufacturer, country of origin and care instructions (Vanderhoff, 1988). The Federal Ministry of Industries in Nigeria advocated that comprehensive information and care instructions on locally produced goods including garments should be made available to consumers for wise decisions and proper care (Green, 1983). It is therefore the right of consumers to have access to care instructions on purchased garments or fabrics by the yard. The care label must be attached to the garment where it can be easily seen. If the care label is not easy to see, additional information must appear on the packaging or hang tag fastened to the product. Items that are exempt from the ruling are household textiles, retail items costing less than \$3.00, footwear, head gear, hand coverings and items not used to cover and protect the body including belts, neckties, handkerchiefs, and suspenders (Marshal, Jackson, Stanley, Kefgen, & Tochie-Specht, 2000). Care labels provide warnings if garments cannot be cleaned without harm. Care label also warns consumers about certain procedures that are consistent with the instructions on the label, but could harm the products. Care label information must be given for; Washing or dry cleaning- if only one of these is listed, that is the only method tested and recommended by the manufacturer; Machine or hand wash- If special treatments are required;; Bleaching- if not mentioned, any type of bleach may be used; Tumble drying or

special drying- if special drying temperature or procedures are required, Ironing - if not mentioned, no ironing is required. If ironing, special instructions may also be given (Shin, 2000). Care labels are attached on a garment's seam, neckline, sleeve, or belt. It may also be clipped on a bolt of yard goods or on the transparent wrapper of a packaged garment.

Recently, clothing care labels use symbols developed by the American Society for Testing and Materials to represent care information instead of words as recommended by Federal Trade Commission (ASTM International, 2001 in Reham & Kang, 2018). The care label symbol system is based on six basic symbols used to give care instruction. Lines and dots in the symbols give consumers exact settings within each symbol category. More dots imply higher heat needed during ironing. The more lines that are present the gentler the movement. An X overlaid on a symbol is a warning not to use this process (Marshal et al, 2000).

Nelson (2008) reported that taking proper care of garments through adherence to clothing care label instructions will make garments last longer preventing premature aging. It will stretch clothing budget making provision for attending to other family needs. It will also save the time of having to shop for clothes that will wear out too soon and enables the consumers gain maximally their money's worth on purchased garments. Improper care of garments through none adherence to clothing care label instructions could create problems not only to individuals but to the entire family and the nation at large. Clothing is an indispensable necessity for man. Individuals clothing needs differ. Activities, interests, family

structure (number, ages, and relationships), location or environment, weather or atmospheric condition, culture, lifestyle, income, education and occupation influence clothing needs and determine the quantity and quality of clothing possessed by individuals.

Currently the number of number of women working outside their homes throughout the world is increasing on daily basis (Orr, 2001). These are referred to as working class women and those that are employed and paid by the government are termed Female Civil Servants (FCS). They work in government establishments such as schools, (Primary, Secondary, Universities and other tertiary institutions as teachers and lecturers), Ministries and other government agencies. Working .class women play tripartite roles as employees, wives and mothers. Their clothing needs differ significantly from those of non working women. They therefore need and have strong desire for variety of quality and professionally made garments to suit their professions. For FCS to derive maximum satisfaction from clothing purchased, they need to be skillful in the management and care of fabrics and garments in their possession. It is uncertain if FCS in Nsukka adhere to clothing care label instructions in caring for their clothing items.

Objectives of the Study

The study is guided by the following objectives.

1. Identify the awareness of clothing care label instructions adhered to by women in Nsukka
2. Identify the adherence of clothing care labels by respondents in Nsukka LGA on the following areas:(a) Washing, bleaching and dry cleaning, (b) bleaching and (c)

3. Determine the problems encountered by women for effective clothing care label instruction adherence in Nsukka LGA of Enugu State.

Hypotheses: The following null hypotheses were tested by the study at 0.05 level of Significance.

H₀1: There are no significant difference in adherence to washing, bleaching, dry-cleaning, drying and ironing adherence practices to clothing care label instruction between WA and WAP.

Methodology

Research Design: The study adopted a cross sectional survey design, which is used to gather information between two groups of a representative sample regarding their attitude, habits and opinion over a matter under investigation. The result of such findings is generalizable to a larger population.

Area of the Study: The study was carried out in Nsukka, Nsukka Local Government Area of Enugu State, Nigeria. Nsukka is the location to the premier University of Nigeria, Colleges of Education and other primary and post - primary and secondary schools. These institutions readily provided the respondents for women in academics and administrative positions.

Population for the Study: The target population included two categories of: working class women in academics (WA) comprising lecturers from University of Nigeria, College of Education and teachers in various post primary schools all in Nsukka urban. The second category was working class women in administrative positions (WAP) in the same institutions. These categories of

women were used are educated and are expected to read, understand and adhere to care label instructions attached to their ready to wear garments.

Sample for the Study: Stratified random sampling technique was used to select women working in different government parastatal in the study area including tertiary and post primary schools, ministries of education and health. The sample included 80 female lecturers from University of Nigeria, Nsukka College of Education and teachers from the post- secondary schools. 80 women in the administrative position were also randomly selected from the same institutions. The total sample for the study was 160

Instrument for Data Collection: Data were collected using Clothing Care Label Instruction Adherence (CCLIA) questionnaire. The instrument was made up of 88 question items divided into three sections. Section A comprised personal data of respondents. Section B dealt with clothing care label instruction and practices of the respondents and section C focused on problems militating against effective

clothing care label instruction adherence practices. The questions were structured using dichotomous response modes in sections A and B while section C was structured using 4-point rating scale where 4 point indicates strongly agree, 3 point indicates agree, 2 indicates disagree and 1 strongly disagree. The instrument was face validated by three experts in clothing and textiles to ensure validity of the study findings.

Method of data Collection: A total of 160 copies of questionnaire were distributed to the subjects with the help of a research assistant. Some questionnaires were collected on the spot after completely filled by the subjects while others were collected at a later date convenient for the respondents. A 100 percent return was achieved.

Method of Data Analysis: Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (percentages, mean and standard deviation). The Mean value 2.5 and 50 percent or above were cut off values for accepted options. t-test statistics tested the one hypotheses of the study at 0.05 level of significance.

Table1: Percentage Responses of FCS in Nsukka LGA on Awareness of Clothing Care

S/N	Clothing Care Label Awareness	F	%
1	Do you buy ready to wear garment?	150	93.8
2	Do your newly Purchased ready to wear garments have care labels attached to them?	138	86.2
3	Do you read the clothing care label instruction on your newly purchased ready to wear garments?	68	42.5
4	When buying fabrics by the yards, do sellers give or show you care label for the fabrics?	0	0
5	How often do you purchase ready to wear garments		
i	Every month	2	1.2
ii	Every 3 months	8	5.0
iii	Every 6 months	21	13.1
iv	Every 9 months	31	19.4
6	How many ready to wear garments do you purchase in a year?		
i	1-5	99	61.9
ii	6-10	60	37.5
iii	11-15	1	.6

Table 1 indicate that 93.8% buy ready to wear garments, 82.2% purchase garments with care instruction, 42.5% read care label information or instruction attached to the garment before washing, bleaching, dry cleaning, drying or ironing the garments and none of the respondents' was shown

or given care label or care information on how to care for the fabrics when buying fabrics by the yard. Majority of the respondents (61.2%), buy garments once in a year and about 1to5 garments in one year (61.9%).

Table 2: Percentage Responses Results of WA and WAP on adherence to washing instruction in care label

A	Washing Instructions	WA	%	WAP	%
1	Machine wash Normal	32	20.2	19	11.9
2	Machine wash cold	18	11.2	20	12.5
3	Machine wash warm	34	21.2	31	19.4
4	Machine wash hot	40	25.0	30	18.8
5	Hotness not to exceed 50° C	27	16.9	24	15.0
6	Hotness not to exceed 60° C	26	16.2	25	15.6
7	Hotness not to exceed 70° C	23	14.4	18	11.2
8	Machine wash, permanent press	24	15.0	34	21.2
9	Machine wash , gentle or delicate	29	18.1	27	16.9
10	Hand wash	39	24.4	30	18.8
11	Do not wash at all	27	16.9	28	17.5

Key: Waf-Working Class Women in academics frequency counts, %- Percentages, WAPf- Working Class Women in administrative positions frequency counts, Of-

Observed frequency, Ef- Expected frequency, P-val- P- value, Sig- Significant level, S- significant, NS- Non significant.

Data in Table 2 above reveal that none of the washing instructions attracted high

percentage score up to 50 percent by both categories of respondents. The washing instruction that attracted highest score though not up to acceptable cut off was machine wash hot by WA (25%).

Table 3: Percentage Responses Results of WA and WAP on adherence to bleaching and dry cleaning instructions in care label

S/N	Care Label Instructions Adherence	WA	%	WAP	%
B	Bleaching Instructions				
1	Any bleach can be used	22	13.8	23	14.4
2	Use only non-chlorine bleach	17	10.6	16	10.0
3	Do not bleach	22	13.8	20	12.5
	Dry Cleaning Instructions				
1	Dry clean	34	21.2	23	14.4
2	Dry clean using any solvent	26	16.2	16	10.0
3	Use Petroleum solvents only	18	11.2	17	10.6
4	Use any solvent except Trichloroethylene	17	10.6	12	7.5
5	Dry clean, short cycle	16	10.0	11	6.9
6	Dry clean, reduced moisture	21	13.1	12	7.5
7	Dry clean, low heat	17	10.6	17	10.6
8	Do not dry clean	21	13.1	23	14.4

Table 3 presented data on respondents' responses on their care label instruction adherence to bleaching and dry cleaning. It was revealed that none of the bleaching and dry cleaning instructions attracted

high score of being adhered to by both categories of respondents. The care instruction least adhered to by both WA and WAP was 'dry clean short cycle' (10.0 and 6.9 respectively).

Table 4: Percentage Responses Results of WA and WAP on adherence to bleaching and drying instructions in care label

D	Drying Instructions	WA	%	WAP	%
1	Tumble dry, no	32	20.2	19	11.9
2	Tumble dry, permanent press	18	11.2	20	12.5
3	Dry on a line	34	21.2	31	19.4
4	Tumble dry No heat	40	25.0	30	18.8
5	Dry in a shade	27	16.9	24	15.0
6	Do not dry	26	16.2	25	15.6
7	Tumble dry, normal, low heat	23	14.4	18	11.2
8	Drip Dry	24	15.0	34	21.2
9	Dry flat	29	18.1	27	16.9

The data on the above Table indicate that 25% of WA adhere to the “tumble dry, no heat” drying instruction more than any other drying instruction where as the

highest percentage of WAP (21.2%) drip dry their garments following the instruction in the care label

Table 5: Percentage Responses of WA and WAP on adherence to bleaching and ironing instructions in care label

E	Ironing/Pressing Instructions	WA	%	WAP	%
1	Iron, any temperature, steam/dry	49	30.6	53	33.1
2	Iron steam or dry with low heat	60	37.5	60	37.5
3	Can use medium heat	56	35.0	55	34.4
4	Can use high heat	27	16.9	34	21.2
5	Do not iron with steam	36	22.5	43	26.9
6	Do not Iron	23	14.4	19	11.9

It was observed that majority of both categories of FCS adhere to “iron steam or dry with low heat ironing instruction in clothing care label while ironing their clothes. This is seen by the high score (37.5% each) though not up to 50% acceptable percentage. The care label instruction least adhered to by both WA and WAP was “Do not iron” (14.4% and 11.9 respectively).

Ho₁: There are no significant differences in Percentage responses of WA and WAP

in Nsukka on their adherence to washing, bleaching and dry cleaning, drying and ironing care label instruction in clothing care.

The X² P-values of 0.47 for washing, 0.80 for bleaching, 0.43 for dry cleaning, 0.52 for drying and 0.56 for ironing are greater than 0.05 (P>0.05) at a degree of freedom 1 each. The hypothesis stating there are no significant differences in percentage responses of WA and WAP in Nsukka are thereby accepted in all instances.

Table 3A: Mean Responses and t-test Results of WA and WAP on Problems Militating Against Effective Adherence to Clothing Care Label Instructions in Clothing Care (N=160), ($X_1=80$), ($X_{11}=80$), (Df= 158)

Washing instruction related problems	X₁	Sd₁	X₁₁	Sd₁₁	X₁₁₁	Sd₁₁₁	t-cal	P-value	P-val
Difficulty in interpreting the washing instructions and symbols	3.12	.537	3.11	.636	3.12	0.58	.134	.893	.893
Don't remember to read care label before washing the garment	3.21	.650	3.04	.803	3.13	.727	1.515	.132	.132
Texture of garment fabric sag or stretch with incorrect laundry procedure	3.31	.466	3.39	.490	3.35	.478	-.991	.323	.323
Garment cannot withstand the stated washing procedure	3.19	.480	3.01	.405	3.10	.443	2.492	.014	.014
Difficulty in differentiating hard and soft water which negatively affect the result of laundry	2.01	.584	1.94	.332	1.88	.608	.998	.320	.320
Colour loss due to wrong choice of washing temperature/soap /detergent.	3.11	.390	3.10	.467	3.10	.428	.184	.854	.854
Colour transfer due to wrong choice of washing /laundry procedure.	3.08	.382	3.06	.401	3.07	.391	.202	.840	.840
Difficulty in manipulating washing machine	2.80	.644	2.79	.589	2.78	.616	.128	.898	.898
Bleaching instruction related problems									
Fabric changes colour due to wrong fabric bleaching procedure (Non-white fabric changes to dirty and parched white).	3.19	.480	3.18	.497	3.18	.489	.162	.822	.822
Some non-bleachable garments when bleached damage fabric texture.	3.14	.497	3.06	.460	3.10	.478	.991	.323	.323
Dry cleaning Instruction related problems									
Colour loss if 'dry cleanable only' garments are washed	3.04	.583	3.10	.608	3.07	.596	-.663	.508	.508
Loss of fabric texture if 'dry cleanable only' garments are washed	3.06	.536	3.18	.444	3.12	.490	1.446	.150	.150
Loss of garment colour and texture with wrong choice of dry cleaning solvents.	3.10	.467	3.08	.444	3.09	.455	.347	.729	.729
Drying Related Problems									
Permanent wrinkles often occur with incorrect machine drying	3.18	.591	3.22	.527	3.20	.559	-.565	.573	.573

Table 3B: Mean Responses and t-test Results of WA and WAP on Problems Militating Against Effective Adherence to Clothing Care Label Instructions in Clothing Care (N=160), (X₁=80), (X₁₁=80), (Df= 158)

Some fabric shrink and reduce in size after washing and drying if not pre-treated	3.62	.487	3.46	.526	3.54	.507	2.027	.044	.044
Stretchy fabrics (e.g . wool) sag with incorrect drying method	3.69	.466	3.65	.480	3.77	.473	.501	.617	.617
Ironing Related Problems									
Fabric burns because fibre cannot withstand hot iron temperature.	3.71	.455	3.61	.490	3.66	.473	1.337	.183	.183
Fabric scotches or presents press marks or shine on ironing non- iron able fabrics with hot temperature.	3.66	.476	3.55	.501	3.61	.489	1.457	.147	.147
Wool and synthetic fabrics mart, cake or bore holes with incorrect ironing temperature.	3.54	.502	3.51	.503	3.53	.502	.315	.735	.735
Premature ageing of clothing items	3.44	.548	3.50	.503	3.97	.525	-.752	.453	.453
Manufacturers/garment or fabric sellers' related problems									
Many imported or locally made ready to wear garments lack clothing care label information or instructions.	3.41	.520	3.31	.587	3.36	.503	1.141	.256	.256
Difficulty in understanding or interpreting some clothing care instruction symbols.	2.81	.506	2.71	.532	2.76	.519	1.218	.225	.225
Wrong care information (Clothes are sometimes mislabeled)	2.52	.527	2.61	.515	2.57	.521	1.062	.290	.290
Locally made ready to wear garments carry decorative labels rather than care information	3.39	.487	3.29	.455	3.35	.471	1.173	.242	.242
Fabric sellers fail to attach care instructions to bolts of fabrics when selling fabrics by the yards to consumers.	3.49	.528	3.41	.495	3.45	.511	.927	.355	.355

Key: N- Number of respondents, X₁-Mean for women in academics, Sd₁-Standard deviation for women in academics, X₁₁-

Mean for women in administrative positions, Sd₁₁- Standard deviation for women in administrative positions, X₁₁₁-

Grand Mean for WA and WAP, Sd_{111} - Standard deviation for X_{111} , t -cal - T -calculated, P -val- P -value, df - Degree of freedom.

Data in Table 6 above reveal that 25 out of 30 identified clothing care label instruction adherence related problems were rated highly above mean 3 by both WA and WAP. This is revealed by the grand means of the scores. The most highly rated problem by both categories of respondents was premature aging of the garment or fabric with non adherence to ironing care label instructions ($3.97 \pm .53$), followed by stretchy fabrics (e.g wool) sag with incorrect drying method ($3.77 \pm .47$). The least rated problem by the respondents was the difficulty in differentiating hard and soft water for washing which negatively affect the result of laundry ($1.88 \pm$). All the identified bleaching, dry cleaning and drying related problems were rated highly.

Discussion

The study findings reveal that majority (93%) of the FCS in the study area buy ready to wear garments, approximately one to five with care labels in a year. This finding indicates that the requirement to attach care information or instruction on wearing apparel for consumers wise purchasing and consumption decisions as reported by Green (1983) is being adhered to by garment manufacturers. However, yard or piece goods lack care information and locally made ready to wear garments carry labels without care instructions or information as none of the FCS was given or shown care information or instruction when buying fabrics by the yard. This finding supports Inyang (2004) observation on non-availability of fibre contents and cleaning instructions on locally produced goods including clothing and textile products

The finding revealed that only very few (42.5%) of FCS who purchase few ready to wear garments with care label (1-5 in a year), read the information before washing, bleaching, dry-cleaning, drying and ironing their garments. Weber (1990) reveals that inability of reading care information is the biggest problem with clothing consumers. Label information and reactions to revised Canadian General Standards Board (CGSB) care label symbol, found that majority of the respondents (67%) use care information when purchasing apparel. However, respondents' reactions to the new CGSB symbols indicated a high level of non-comprehension which also supports the finding of the present study.

Regarding clothing care label instruction adherence in clothing care by FCS, findings show that none of the 30 identified care instructions and symbols categorized under washing, bleaching, dry cleaning, drying and ironing scored highly up to 50 percent. The failure of consumers to read clothing care label information, instructions or guide on purchased fabrics and garments and unavailability of care label to read by clothing consumers predispose negative consequences or post purchase dissonance (McNeal and McDonald, 1982). Johnson & Foster (1990), warned that a consumer who is careless about reading care instructions must take the responsibilities.

Johnson and Foster (1990), warns that should one assume that a garment that says 'machine wash' can also be dry cleaned, the dyes that are fine for washing may dissolve in dry cleaning fluids. Continuing, they warned that if a care label says dry clean, and the fibre contents can be washed safely, the garment might contain several fabrics such as interfacings and trims which

shrink more than the other causing puckering problems using washing rather than dry cleaning. This implies that non adherence to clothing care instructions poses threat to clothing consumers.

On the problems encountered on adherence to clothing care labels, these problems have been extensively acknowledged by McGraw-Hill (1982), Weber (1990), Johnson & Foster (1990), Marshal et al (2000), and Nelson, (2013). The t-test results revealed no significant differences in the mean responses of WA and WAP on problems militating against adherence to care label instruction in clothing care. These findings have implications to the clothing manufacturers, retailers, consumers, Standard organization of Nigeria (SON). In developed countries including United States of America, consumers rights on textile wearing apparel are protected by enforcement of the US Federal Trade Commission Act which empowers the Commission, among others to; prevent unfair methods of competition and unfair or deceptive acts or practices in or affecting commerce; seek monetary redress and other relief for conduct injurious to consumers; prescribe rules defining with specificity acts or practices that are unfair or deceptive, and establishing requirements designed to prevent such acts or practices; gather and compile information and conduct investigations relating to the organization, business, practices, and management of entities engaged in commerce; and make reports and legislative recommendations to Congress and the public (FTC, 2000).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Findings from this study have clearly shown that FCS in Nsukka LGA of Enugu state buy ready to wear garments with care label. Clothing care adherence saves

a lot of damage on clothing. Care label instructions were not adhered to by FCS precipitating to 43 identified clothing care instruction adherence related problems encountered in clothing care. Based on the conclusion, it was recommended that:

1. Clothing and textiles manufacturers should help consumers by including care information instruction details in every garment or fabrics by the yards in simple and clear English and attach them where it will be visible for consumers.
2. Retailers should insist on collecting from clothing manufacturers care labels for those clothing items which care label were not attached so that they dispose them to consumers during purchase.
3. Clothing consumers should not buy garments or fabrics by the yard (yard goods) without care label stating clearly care instructions. If any damage occurs on purchased garment or fabric as a result of wrong care instruction, return and refund should be sought from the manufacturer but if damage occurs as a result of non-adherence to care instruction, consumer should take responsibility.
4. To enhance consumer right protection, Standard Organization of Nigeria should also extend its services to inspecting the quality of clothing imported into the country and those produced locally to ensure they meet international standard in terms of care information provided.
5. Clothing and textile teachers and lecturers at all levels of education can organize sensitization through seminars, workshops, women conferences and meetings on the need for adhering to care label instruction in clothing care.

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